

No Justice, No Peace? A Challenge for Syria

Emily K. M. Scott

Emily Scott is Associate Professor of International Development at the University of Birmingham, United Kingdom. Her research concerns humanitarianism, conflict, and organizational behavior, with particular focus on the protection of civilians, health, and migration in MENA. Her work was most recently published in journals including Perspectives on Politics, Global Studies Quarterly, and World Development.

Introduction

In 2011, Syria's nonviolent movement was unsuccessful in its attempt to peacefully overthrow the government. Violent repression of the movement escalated into a civil war between the government and rebel groups. Now, more than a decade after the uprising began, Syria's rebels join the ranks of the few violent movements that have succeeded in toppling a government since 2010. The country's recovery will be more challenging than it would have been following peaceful civil resistance (Chenoweth 2020).

Societies affected by killing, wounding, and death continue to suffer the physiological and psychosocial effects after conflict ends (Collier et al. 2008), with families and communities broken up and violence becoming a common response to injustice. Production, labour, transport, communication, and infrastructures need rebuilding, and this puts economies under pressure, causing life expectancy to drop during transitions out of violent resistance, more than out of non-violence (Stoddard 2013). Regimes that fall due to violent civil resistance also develop higher levels of autocracy than those that fall through peaceful resistance (Tarrow 2007).

In Syria today, there are signs that a demo-

cratic veneer is being used to cover autocratic consolidation by the al-Sharaa government in Syria, making rights groups “wary” (MacDonald 2025). The interim electoral system has been described as based on both “selection and election,” with interim President al-Sharaa directly appointing one-third of parliament and province-level electoral bodies formed by the government tasked with selecting the remaining two-thirds. Structures of power are also being centralized around al-Sharaa and his brothers, while Hayat Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) loyalists hold key ministries, including defense, foreign affairs, and interior (Abdulrahim 2025).

The presence of very limited minority group members and just one woman in the interim cabinet suggests inclusion is a low priority. This curt nod to religious, ethnic, and gender representation in the cabinet may appease international observers while Syria trends toward authoritarianism (ETANA 2025). In fact, analysts warn that HTS is consolidating power by “gaining external recognition and legitimation to foster its domination within the country” (Daher 2025) — a task helped by democratic signaling.

When process-based inclusion is lacking — that is, when minority and citizen voices are not let into decision-making — there is a risk that outcomes, such as social welfare, educ-

ation, health, and economic growth, as well as justice and accountability, will be distributed to preferred groups. Additionally, any distributions of outcomes along religious or ethnic lines have the potential to deepen divides already threatening the stability of Syria's transition, and reminiscent of Ba'athist policies which exploited kin and clientelist networks (Neep 2025; Hinnebusch 2021).

Sectarian violence has been escalating in the last six months. In June 2025, the Mar Elias Church in Damascus was attacked, killing 25 people and injuring 63, in the first attack in Damascus since the overthrow of Assad and possibly the work of the Islamic State (IS), or Saraya Ansar al-Sunnah, a splinter group of HTS that may have ties to IS (Zelin 2025b). In Sweida, deadly clashes between Bedouin tribes and the Druze minority broke out in July, with government-affiliated forces soon implicated in the March 6th massacre of hundreds of 'Alawite civilians on the Syrian coast (Zelin 2025a). The Syrian Network for Human Rights recorded 2818 civilians killed across the country in the first half of 2025 (SNHR 2025a).

The SNHR has called on the government to “regulate the use of force” and work toward accountability and community trust in justice institutions through “open, independent, and transparent investigations into all reported violations, including extrajudicial killings, abductions, arbitrary detention, and degrading treatment” (SNHR 2025b).

Syria's transition is occurring while the global order is trending toward foreign aid reductions, military spending, protection, and autocratization. Dominant neo-liberal democratic ideals underpinning foreign policymaking are weak. Yet, global interest in a democratic transition in Syria remains high

because of its geostrategic position in the MENA region and shifts in alliances triggered by the regime's fall, as well as some recognition of what is owed to Syrians who rose up and fought to topple a brutal dictatorship. How will these tensions be resolved?

A Democratic Future?

Democratization in conflict-affected settings can lead to the recurrence of civil war. Theoretically, democracy offers alternatives to violence as a mechanism for resolving disputes and addressing sources of conflict through democratized resource and benefit sharing (Hegre 2014). In practice, elections often generate new violence in countries recovering from civil war (Höglund et al. 2009), with long-term stability more likely in high-income, older, consolidated democracies: “democratic strategies for maintaining order may be more costly than the autocratic strategies” (Hegre 2014, 167).

Still, scholars know that strong institutions that are representative of the population can also help reduce fear (Mattes and Savun 2009), and support groups in making more credible and transparent commitments (Bara et al. 2021; Suhrke and Berdal 2013). They can make it harder for grievances to inspire violence (Boyle 2014; Steenkamp 2014). Where women are represented in post-war institutions, peace may be prolonged (Shair-Rosenfield and Wood 2017). Strong law enforcement institutions make engaging in violence—including non-political crime—more costly (Gartner and Kennedy 2018).

So, what should scholars and analysts say about the democratic future of Syria? We must understand and point to parallel imperatives to champion accountability and justice. Any transition to democracy must be gradual

(Carothers 2007), locally driven, and coupled with efforts to strengthen institutions and foster peace (Mross 2019).

Questions about Syria's future regime type and power structures are important, and matter to the press, the public, and, most importantly, Syrians. But, as scholars of the Middle East, it is crucial that we continue to champion Syrian human rights, civil society, community, and diaspora actors' calls for justice and accountability. In this moment of foreign aid and democratic retrenchment, relying on and supporting local action is more important than ever.

Justice and Accountability

Article 49 of the Syrian Constitutional Declaration specifies, "A transitional justice commission shall be established, adopting effective, victim-centered mechanisms to determine accountability mechanisms, the right to know the truth, and justice for victims and survivors, in addition to honoring martyrs." (Presidency of the Syrian Arab Republic Declaration 2025, 14). National Commissions for Transitional Justice and for the Missing were established by presidential decree in May and are meant to produce accountability and justice for past crimes, and to govern future conduct of the Syrian state.

The founder of the civil society group Syrian Network for Human Rights has, however, argued that the establishment of these bodies by presidential decree and not through a legislative council may make it harder to center Syrian national ownership, protect independence from the executive and the ministry of justice, and better guarantee funding (Abdulghany 2025). He wrote of the need for these Commissions to hold a range of investigative powers: "This is particularly important given

the priority of accessing documents from security branches, prisons, hospitals, and courts, which addresses the challenge of accessing archives that typically arises in contexts where previous authorities have deliberately concealed or destroyed official records" (*Ibid.*).

The International Center for Transitional Justice highlighted the need for inquiries to be grounded in affected communities, coordinate with civil society actors and international institutions, and for the Commissions to be inclusive in their engagement and outreach (ICTJ 2025). Meanwhile, survivor-led accountability movements that have formed throughout the last decade require pathways to inclusion (Bernath 2025), and there is a need to protect the independence and documentation of atrocity crimes created by the Syrian White Helmets—a challenge given the organization voted overwhelmingly to be integrated into the new government.

These are just a few of the pressing justice and accountability challenges in Syria.

Conclusion

In the absence of justice, there will be no peace. Principles of truth, justice, and accountability, and the laws and norms that underpin them, are under threat globally. Yet, scholars interested in supporting the calls of Syrians can build and share knowledge about how representation, accountability, justice, and peace can be achieved in Syria, even while the globe trends toward impunity. ♦

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